

Applications of Refractive Index in the Study of Chemical Constitution. Part I. The Constant K and Straight Line Mixture Law for Liquid-liquid Mixtures

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The new function, K_r , has been applied in about fourteen liquid-liquid mixtures and the results show that the straight line mixture law is appreciably applicable.

Joshi and Joshi¹ suggested a new function $K_r = M/(n^2 + 2)$ at a constant temperature for the study of chemical constitution and evaluated the atomic, group, and structural values for n_D^{20} values. In the present work several liquid-liquid mixtures, for which this function has been applied, are discussed.

The straight line mixture law is given by

$$K_{r(m)} = f \cdot K_{r(s)} + (1-f)K_{r(l)}$$

where $K_{r(m)}$, $K_{r(s)}$, and $K_{r(l)}$ are the values for the mixture, solute, and solvent respectively and f is the mole fraction of the solute.

The values of $K_{r(m)}$, $K_{r(s)}$, and f were determined experimentally and $K_{r(s)}$ was evaluated by using the above formula. The value of $K_{r(s)}$ was also determined experimentally and also calculated from the atomic, group, and structural values where data were available. It was pointed out in a previous communication¹ that this constant K_r , because of lesser number of experimental determinations, had an obvious advantage over the Lorenz-Lorentz function:

$$R_L = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d}$$

A comparison of the additivity relation in case of the constants K_r and R_L for six mixtures, the data for which were reported in another connection², is shown in Table I. The values of $K_{r(s)}$ and $R_{L(s)}$ are obtained from mixtures and in cases where their values are seen to be influenced regularly by varying concentration, the extrapolated (exptd.) values are given instead of the mean value. The calculated values of $R_{L(s)}$ are from the R_L equivalents reported by Vogel³.

It is evident from these results that the mixture law is better applicable for the function K_r than for R_L . Conclusions for eight mixtures, in which the function K_r only has been applied, are reported in Table II which indicates that the mixture law is appreciably applicable, particularly in concentrated solutions. In the case of methyl and ethyl acetoacetates, the calculated value of the keto form is, as anticipated, higher than the observed value or values obtained from the solution. In case of solutions like *o*-chlorophenol in benzene, aniline in *p*-dioxane, the effect of the polar component

1. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 57.

2. *Ibid.*, 1962, 39, 136.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1842.

is noticeable, but the mixture law is applicable in concentrated solutions. In such cases the value of $K^{(c)}$ is obtained by extrapolation (exptd.).

TABLE I

<i>m.f.</i>	$K_r(x)$	$R_L(x)$	
I. Nitrobenzene in aniline.			
0.08381	28.12	33.20	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 27.91; exptd. = 27.00; calc. = 27.92.
0.14012	27.92	32.80	
0.53797	27.91	32.46	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 32.71; exptd. = 31.19; calc. = 31.97.
II. Chlorobenzene in aniline.			
0.11230	26.25	30.80	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 26.01; mean = 26.08; calc. = 26.07.
0.38832	25.99	31.38	
0.84608	26.01	31.30	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 31.19; mean = 31.13; calc. = 31.11.
III. Bromobenzene in aniline.			
0.07561	35.77	39.8*	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 35.42; exptd. = 35.41; calc. = 35.42.
0.57432	35.56	33.9	
0.87787	35.45	34.1	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 34.0; exptd. = 34.19 (excluding*); calc. = 34.0.
IV. <i>m</i> -Cresol in benzene.			
0.04448	24.73	34.30	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 24.75; mean = 24.74; calc. = 24.72.
0.10286	24.76	33.30	
0.02431	24.72	32.78	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 32.73; exptd. = 32.05; calc. = 32.45.
V. Anilina in benzene.			
0.01388	20.73	28.77	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 20.63; mean = 20.58; calc. = 20.63.
0.32834	20.40	30.06	
0.86555	20.60	30.63	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 30.49; exptd. = 30.76; calc. = 29.70.
VI. Chlorobenzene in nitrobenzene.			
0.16080	26.07	31.13	$K_r(x)$: obs. = 26.01; exptd. = 26.00; calc. = 25.95.
0.48823	26.04	31.11	
0.88188	26.02	31.10	$R_L(x)$: obs. = 31.19; exptd. = 31.00; calc. = 31.11.

TABLE II

S.No.	Mixture.	$K_r(x)$		
		From soln.	Obs.	Calc.
1	<i>p</i> -Dioxane in benzene	21.77 (mean)	27.89	..
2	Heptane ^a in <i>p</i> -dioxane	25.59 (exptd.)	25.51	25.51
3	Benzaldehyde in benzene	24.14 (,,)	24.17	..
4	Methyl acetoacetate in benzene	29.04 (,,)	28.94	29.20 (for keto form)
5	Ethyl acetoacetate in benzene	32.64 (,,)	32.45	32.57 (for keto form)
6	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol in benzene	29.13 (mean)	29.02	..
7	Aniline in <i>p</i> -dioxane	20.19 (,,)	20.63	20.63
8	Aniline in CCl ₄	21.57 (,,)	20.63	20.63

The data obtained by Williams and Krachms⁴ have been tried in case of fifteen liquid-liquid mixtures and these also have proved that the function is appreciably applicable in the liquid-liquid mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Laboratory chemicals of A. R. quality, either B. D. H. or Merck, were mostly used and in some cases the pure laboratory chemicals were purified by distillation in pyrex distilling apparatus. The temperature was maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulating thermostated water through the prism box of the Abbe refractometer and the chemicals were also maintained at the requisite temperature (20°) by keeping them in the thermostat. n_D^{20} was measured with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 .

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